

Narcissism as the Moral Blindness of Modern Culture

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Your business is to fix his attention on the stream of immediate sense experiences. Teach him to call it ‘real life’ and don’t let him ask what he means by ‘real’.

(Lewis 1942, 2)

Abstract

The article examines how narcissism – understood not only as a psychological phenomenon but also as a cultural pattern – becomes a mechanism of moral blindness. The belief is presented that in the environment of digital self-presentation, social bubbles, and relativisation of truth, the categories of good and evil are transformed into aesthetic categories, which ultimately weakens a person’s ability to judge between good and evil, reduces the space for guilt, and blurs the imperative of responsible action. This study moves at the intersection of philosophy, ethics, theology, and social psychology, and highlights the need for a renaissance of metaphysics as a basis for the renewal of the categories of truth and goodness.

Keywords

Narcissism; education; teaching; moral philosophy; theology; subjectivism; truth; metaphysics

Introduction

The idea from C S Lewis in the motto of this study corresponds brilliantly with the state of contemporary culture. Evil is not presented as an open rebellion against good, but in the account of “experienced devil” advising the young demon, evil is a gradual weakening of man’s ability to persist in the question of truth and interest in objective reality. According to Lewis, distraction does not mean merely turning attention away, but a constant interruption in the relationship between mind and reality. Evil thus manifests itself as a disintegration of man’s inner unity, which ultimately prevents him from encountering that which transcends him. Truth does not become “denied” and “rejected”, but irrelevant, and moral decision-making thus shifts from the level of knowledge to the level of immediate impulses and emotional experiences, which ultimately leads to a weakening of man’s responsibility.

We live in a culture that is usually referred to as post-factual¹. This expresses the fact that in our “philosophical environment” facts lose their authoritative power, the question of objective

¹ This term was occasionally used as early as the 1990s, but it was introduced into widespread academic and media use mainly by the British publicist Ralph Keyes, who published the book *The Post-Truth Era in 2004*. A key moment of public recognition came in 2016 when Oxford Dictionaries declared *post-truth* the “word of the year”.

truth is not decisive, because subjective feelings “from reality”, the power of emotions, personal beliefs and preferences, but also the understanding of one’s own identity come to the fore. Truth is no longer understood as something that is “outside” us and that transcends us, but as something that we construct and create ourselves.

At the same time, we are witnessing an unprecedented rise of narcissism – not just as an individual psychological trait, but as a cultural ideal. Being seen, validated, and admired becomes a basic need that corresponds to the phenomenon of narcissism. Digital technologies, social networks, and the attention economy continue to systematically support this need. Exaggerated individualism, comparing oneself with others in the online space creates a suitable breeding ground in which narcissism becomes an unmistakable challenge (Beck & Beck-Gernsheim 2002).

Narcissism, in the sense of a solipsistic perception of the interpersonal and intrapersonal world, represents a rather serious obstacle to a person’s ability to epistemologically and existentially relate to the world of which he is a part. Since the question of good and evil represents the basic platform from which everything else grows in a certain way as a “superstructure”, we consider it crucial to focus our attention on the place of narcissism in the dialectic of moral philosophy in an age that relativizes truth and absolutizes the ego of man.

Historical context

If we look at classical ethics – from Aristotle to Kant – we see that truth played a normative function, there. The truth was not only a description of reality, a free interpretation of the observed reality, but above all a landmark for action. It was not a “product” of human endeavour, but the “goal” of human cognition, from which everything else unfolded. To know the truth, therefore, meant to be existentially bound to it and to act on it.

The rise of Cartesian rationalism in Europe overshadowed the reality of the human soul. Human reason became the main source of knowledge, and as a result, only what could be rationally justified and logically proved began to be considered true and meaningful. What about spirituality? In the field of epistemology, it gradually entered the sphere of emotions, feelings, and fantasy. The image of man was thus imaginarily divided into two parts (rational – emotional), and the unified image of the world was also shattered (natural – supernatural).

A natural consequence of the emphasis on the rationality of man is the strengthening of the Kantian autonomy of man, to the point that man, without attachment to transcendent reality, is perceived as an independent being in an absolute sense. This shift is aptly expressed by Sartre – “There is no human nature, because there is no God to have a conception of it... Man is nothing else but that which he makes of himself” (Sartre 2007, 4). The shift from heteronomous ethics to autonomous ethics creates space for the belief that only man himself can determine, formulate, and promote values that he himself subsequently considers moral and correct. In a certain sense, man is not only allowed to do so, but it is even his duty and an expression of his

The trigger was political events – Brexit and the US presidential election – in which the massive spread of disinformation and emotional manipulation turned out to be a significant factor influencing their results.

responsibility for himself and for the world. The problem here is not the emphasis on human responsibility, but the displacement of transcendent reality outside the epistemological radius. The belief in the uniqueness of each individual and that society is primarily there to meet their needs and requirements is the logical outcome of this development.

The problem of truth

It is characteristic of contemporary culture that emotions, personal identity, and subjectivist preferences come into the centre of attention of today's man more than the perception of truth as an objective entity independent of his consciousness. As a result, the perception of good and evil is modified into a variety of forms, becoming more a matter of taste, preferential interpretation, or "authenticity" anchored in subjectivism, than of a moral reality that transcends our interpretations. McIntyre (2018) defines post factuality as a situation in contemporary culture where facts exist but are systematically relativized and ignored. The problem is not the absence of "data", but their interpretation, which is not grounded in metaphysics.

In his concept of "liquid modernity", Bauman analyses the phenomenon of instability of contemporary culture in the field of values, identity, and perception of truth (Bauman 2000). He captured very well the issue of post-factual culture, in which truth turns into an instrument of power in human hands, a product, a construct, a commodity that can be traded. It is not evaluated according to conformity with reality, but according to effect, outcome, and utility. Thus, "true" is what works, what mobilizes, what affirms identity, what strengthens emotion, what brings profit and personal benefit.

In his theory of simulations, Baudrillard argues that in postmodern culture it is no longer a representation of reality, but of "simulacra" that replace reality – hyperreality arises, where the distinction between reality and its image disappears (Baudrillard 1994). Rorty's neo-pragmatic relativism leads to similar conclusions, rejecting the understanding of knowledge as a "mirroring of reality" and claiming that truth is rather the result of language games and social agreements (consensus), but it is not a correspondence with objective reality (Rorty 1997). This leads to a rejection of objective reality, preferring instead a subjective realm of perception where the objectivity of the subject under investigation is either tacitly or overtly disavowed.

The image of today's youth

Current technological progress brings unprecedented possibilities and opportunities, to which the young generation reacts sensitively. According to the WHO (2023), mental health problems are most prevalent among young people aged 15–29. It's not just about the accessibility of information, but also about a phenomenon that is coming to the forefront of experts' attention due to undesirable effects resulting from the influences of cyberreality and social media: today's young people are showing a significant increase in the rate of anxiety, depression, loneliness, and identity diffusion (Twenge 2023).

Jonathan Haidt (2024) speaks of "psychological fragility", which is the result of the dynamics of several psychological and sociological factors such as chronic insecurity, pressure to perform, weakening of family structures, and excessive individualism. This is one of the

reasons why the thesis that the crisis of the young generation is not primarily economic or technological, but metaphysical is increasingly emerging in the academic debate (Taylor 2007). It is a crisis of what it means to be human, what our basic values are, what the goal of human life is, and what can be considered true or good or bad.

Psychology can describe symptoms, but it cannot replace questions about the meaning and purpose of life (Illouz 2019). When young people are confronted with suffering or uncertainty, they need answers that are not only behavioural or clinical, but also ontological. The digital environment allows you to constantly create and change your own self-presentation. However, this leads to a split in identity and a loss of authenticity (Turkle 2012)². Young people are immersed in an environment where “reality” has no clear boundaries, which makes stable self-experience impossible, and the feeling of anxiety is exacerbated as a result. Without a metaphysical horizon, there is no solid reason to believe in goodness, truth, or beauty as real entities (Vattimo 2011).

Narcissism as a cultural ideal

The concept of narcissism is associated with the work of Christopher Lasch, who spoke of a “culture of narcissism” as early as the 1970s. Narcissism means not only excessive self-love, but also an exaggerated desire for self-affirmation, which can lead to a deep dependence on “mirroring” on the part of others.

In traditional societies, the human ego was corrected by community, religion, and moral norms. In modern culture, these correctives have been significantly weakened. Individualism and autonomy of man cease to be “balanced” by the relationship to the collective and the demands of the collective on the individual. The goal becomes an autonomous self-actualization of one’s personality.

Today’s highly developed digital culture creates a technical environment in which this self-actualization can be constantly exposed to the audience. A person’s identity becomes more *performative* (I show off my world) than *formative* (I shape my world). A person’s value is measured by visibility and response (likes). Many studies today confirm the negative impact on the psychological development of children and adolescents (Schwartz et al. 2021).

The real causes of narcissism are unknown and yet “narcissistic personality disorder” (NPD) is included in the categorization of psychological personality disorders (Heretik-Heretiková 2021). However, the personality structure of a person with NPD carries an internal paradox: self-confidence on the surface, fragility at the core. On the surface, self-affirmation, at the core, is fear of rejection. The increase in anxiety disorders and self-harm among young people has

² Sherry Turkle in her work *Alone Together* (2012) points out that due to the influence of the digital environment, the boundary between authentic and constructed self becomes blurred. Young people create multiple and diverse identities that are flexible, fragmented, and mostly dependent on feedback from their surroundings. As a result, an internal division occurs – between who a person really is and how they present themselves in the virtual world. Since such “reality” does not guarantee stability, identity consequently becomes unstable, which weakens the awareness of continuity of one’s self and the integrity of personality. The result is increased anxiety, uncertainty, and the need for constant affirmation of one’s own worth through external recognition (being seen, validated, acknowledged).

been confirmed by the professional community and represents a major challenge for family policy and the quality of education.³

Evil as Moral Blindness

Hannah Arendt (2006), in her analysis of totalitarianism introduced the concept of banality of evil by her world-renowned words: “The sad truth is that most evil is done by people who never make up their minds to be either good or evil.” Evil, she argues, does not have to be demonic; it can be the result of an inability to think and judge in terms of consequential reasoning. It is enough to mechanically follow the orders of the “system” without judging whether those instructions are moral or not. According to Arendt, evil does not even have to be a conscious choice, but an absence of reflection and responsibility on the part of man. The motivation of such a person may be indifference, lack of critical thinking, or devotion to a “system of thinking” that is not ontologically tied to the truth (Arendt 1978).

In the post-factual and narcissistic culture, a similar mechanism arises, but on a new basis: it is not an inability to think, but an inability to transcend one’s own ego, one’s own individualistic preferences in the name of the functioning of the whole. The moral blindness of today consists in the fact that the individual is unable to acknowledge anything higher/other than his own perspective. However, if the truth does not go beyond my own experience and my own preferences, then it can neither confront nor convict me. The normativity of good in this way of seeing the world loses the foundation of its reasoning. If another person becomes a backdrop for the affirmation of my “I”, then a culture of dehumanization inevitably occurs. The fragmentation of society, the loss of coherence in a person’s life, is a natural consequence (Zacharias 1997, 137–9).

In theological terminology, according to the creation story of the first chapters of the Book of Genesis, narcissism can be said to be a modern form of temptation to “be like God”—as an autonomous being in the absolute sense of being the measure of everything. It is a projection of the desire for perfection and the absolute categories of goodness, beauty, joy, love, and justice, but without a relationship with its Creator. However, this is an illusion, since the *a priori* state is anchored in the fact that man is a created being. From the perspective of ethical reasoning, narcissism appears as a state in which the ego appropriates the competence to determine universal good and evil. Consequently, heteronomous ethics gives way to autonomous ethics. The tension between descriptive ethics (how it is) and prescriptive ethics (how it ought to be) is reduced to a projection of solipsistic preferences. From the point of view of psychology, it is possible to talk about a mechanism that illuminates the state in which evil

³ The *paradox of narcissistic personality*, as described by clinical studies (Kernberg 1971; Miller et al. 2011), lies in the discrepancy between external self-confidence and internal fragility. Outwardly, an individual appears self-assured and self-affirming, yet internally they are dependent on recognition (which they fundamentally crave) and sensitive to rejection (internal injury). This incongruity leads to anxiety and identity instability. In the context of contemporary culture with its pressure for performance and self-presentation, this consequently results in an increased incidence of anxiety disorders and self-harm (Prinstein 2017; Fontana et al. 2023), which represents a serious concern for educational and developmental systems.

arises without a sense of guilt. Evil without repentance. Evil without a sense of shame. As Pope Leo XIV reminds us – if we turn in on ourselves, we risk falling ill with loneliness, and even a narcissism that is concerned with others only out of self-interest. The other is then reduced to someone from whom we can take, without ever being truly willing to give, to offer ourselves (Cardiel 2025).

Conclusion

Evil in the post-factual era is not primarily radical in the sense of rejecting good but is related to disintegration in such a way that it arises where truth, humanity, and the capacity to think collapse. This is a complex phenomenon that can be better understood considering the following dynamic factors: Post-truth culture fuels narcissism because subjective truth makes itself the supreme authority. Narcissism, in turn, accelerates social fragmentation by undermining solidarity, awareness of shared values, and an attitude of responsibility towards others. Fragmentation is then again translated into “post-truth conditions”, since because of fragmentation, common facts disappear and only isolated stories remain, which reinforce scepticism about objective truth. A death spiral of existential proportions is taking shape and evil thus becomes an invisible product of a self-centred culture.

Theologically, this situation can be justified as *incurvatio in se ipsum*⁴, that is, the curvature of man in himself, the overcoming of which requires a return to truth, reality, and relational openness.

If the core of the problem is the loss of perception of truth and the “enlargement” of the ego, which hedonically focuses on the moment of the present, then the path of restoration will lead in the opposite direction past several stops.

The first will be a return to the notion of truth as something that transcends us and that refers to objective reality. In such a case, the truth ceases to be the property of man and becomes a horizon to which we consciously approach our understanding, decision-making, and action. The metaphysical side of human existence and the world open space for man to stabilize his own identity, understand human dignity, bind ethical norms, and teleological horizon of the meaning of life.

The second milestone of the path of renewal will be the cultivation of man’s humility in the field of knowledge. The ability to say: “I may be wrong” or “I admit that things may be different from how I perceive them” – is a prerequisite for the development of the process of moral cognition and the progress of social relations.

The third aspect is the renewal of conscience. By the term “conscience” we do not understand an inner feeling, but rather the ability to be addressed by another subject and reality that I “do not quite know” but I “come to know”. It is a processual aspect of the existential attitude to

⁴ The Latin term *incurvatio in se ipsum* refers to the anthropological-theological state of a person who is turned into himself instead of openness to God and others. This is one of the most accurate classic diagnoses of sin as self-centeredness and introversion. We find this approach already in the thinking of Augustine of Hippo, but we see a precise formulation of theological connections later in Martin Luther in his commentary on the Letter to the Romans. For more information, see: Jenson, M. (2006). *The gravity of sin: Augustine, Luther, and Barth on “homo incurvatus in se”*. London, UK: T & T Clark.

life, because according to conscience is not a given – it is a task. It must be cultivated, exercised, and above all, it must be listened to in silence (Ricoeur 1992, 341).

Theologically speaking – truth sets us free precisely by freeing us from the “tyranny” of our own ego, especially by revealing the transcendent world of responsible love – “Deep within his conscience man discovers a law which he has not laid upon himself but which he must obey. Its voice, ever calling him to love and to do what is good and to avoid evil, sounds in his heart at the right moment... For man has in his heart a law written by God.” (John Paul II 1993, § 54).

References

- Arendt, Hannah. 2006. *Eichmann in Jerusalem: A Report on the Banality of Evil*. New York: Penguin Books.
- Arendt, Hannah. 1978. *The Life of the Mind: Volume One, Thinking*. New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich.
- Baudrillard, Jean. 1994. *Simulacra and Simulation*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Bauman, Zygmunt. 2000. *Liquid Modernity*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Beck, Ulrich, and Elisabeth Beck-Gernsheim. 2002. *Individualization*. London: SAGE.
- Cardiel, Valentina. 2025. “Pope Leo XIV: Fraternity Is One of the Great Challenges for Contemporary Humanity.” *EWTN*. <https://ewtnvatican.com/articles/pope-leo-fraternity-humanity-challenge>.
- Fontana, Andrea, Beatrice Cianfanelli, Roberta Verbaro, Gaia Cuzzocrea, Ilaria Maria Antonietta Benzi, and Lucia Sideli. 2023. “Two-Wave Stability of Grandiose and Vulnerable Narcissism during Adolescence: The Mediating Role of Empathy.” *Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease* 211 (9): 696–703.
- Haidt, Jonathan. 2024. *The Anxious Generation*. New York: Penguin Press.
- Heretik, Anton, and Antonia Heretiková Marsalová. 2021. *Narcissism*. Bratislava: Icarus.
- Illouz, Eva. 2019. *The End of Love*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Jenson, Matt. 2006. *The Gravity of Sin: Augustine, Luther, and Barth on “Homo Incurvatus in Se”*. London: T & T Clark.
- John Paul II. 1993. *Veritatis Splendor*. Encyclical. Vatican: Libreria Editrice Vaticana.
- Kernberg, Otto F. 1975. *Borderline Conditions and Pathological Narcissism*. New York: Jason Aronson.
- Keyes, Ralph. 2004. *The Post-Truth Era: Dishonesty and Deception in Contemporary Life*. New York: St. Martin’s Press.
- Lasch, Christopher. 1979. *The Culture of Narcissism: American Life in an Age of Diminishing Expectations*. New York: W. W. Norton & Company.
- Lewis, C. S. 1942. *The Screwtape Letters*. London: Geoffrey Bles.
- McIntyre, Lee. 2018. *Post-Truth*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

- Miller, Joshua D., Brent J. Hoffman, Eric T. Gaughan, Brittany Gentile, Jessica Maples, and W. Keith Campbell. 2011. "Grandiose and Vulnerable Narcissism: A Nomological Network Analysis." *Journal of Personality* 79 (5): 1013–1042.
- Prinstein, Mitchell J. 2017. *Popular: The Power of Likability in a Status-Obsessed World*. New York: Viking.
- Ricœur, Paul. 1992. *Oneself as Another*. Translated by Kathleen Blamey. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Rorty, Richard. 1979. *Philosophy and the Mirror of Nature*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Sartre, Jean-Paul. 2007. *Existentialism Is a Humanism*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Schwartz, Seth J., Sara Berman, and Moin Syed. 2021. "Adolescent Identity Development." *Annual Review of Developmental Psychology* 3: 1–28.
- Taylor, Charles. 2007. *A Secular Age*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Turkle, Sherry. 2012. *Alone Together*. New York: Basic Books.
- Twenge, Jean M. 2023. *Generations*. New York: Atria Books.
- Vattimo, Gianni. 2011. *A Farewell to Truth*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Zacharias, Ravi. 1997. *Deliver Us from Evil: Restoring the Soul in a Disintegrating Culture*. Dallas, TX: Word Publishing.
- WHO. 2023. *World Mental Health Report*.

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